

ISic3566

I.Sicily inscription 3566

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Unknown

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337361

1. κοιμητήρη^ν ²⁶κοιμητήρι(ο)^ν²⁶ Βαλερείου

2. κ (αὶ) Εὐκαρπεία[ς — —].

3.

Edition: PHI337362

1. κοιμητήρη^ν ²⁶κοιμητήρι(ο)^ν²⁶ Βαλερεία [ς]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645637

PHI 337361

PHI 337362

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 54.0879

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 2006.0566

Manganaro, G. 2005. Per la storia della Sicilia bilingue in epoca tardoantica: presbiteri cristiani e superstizione giudaizzante nel contado. In Rizzo, F.P.(eds.), *Da abitato in abitato. In itinere fra le più antiche testimonianze cristiane degli Iblei*. Rome. pp. 35-44. At 42 n.34 fig.3-4

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